

Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile

22 September 2025 – Version 1.0

The Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile has been developed by the [IGSN–DataCite Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Community of Practice](#) ('Archaeology CoP'). It aims to standardize the description of archaeological and cultural heritage samples, taking in account disciplinary-specific use cases and workflows.

The IGSN–DataCite Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Community of Practice

The Archaeology CoP has been meeting monthly since March 2022. It is composed of a small group of archaeologists and cultural heritage researchers with backgrounds in areas such as archaeometry, landscape archaeology, and data management from prehistoric to modern eras, and with an interest in material sample management, data collection, and publication.

Overview of Version 1.0

Cite As

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Version 1.0 is the first published version of the Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile. It has been released alongside Version 1.0 of the [IGSN Archaeology CoP Crosswalk Recommendation](#) that translates the Metadata Profile into [DataCite Metadata Schema V4.6](#) for the purposes of registering IGSN IDs for archaeological samples.

The members of the Archaeology CoP at the time of publication of Archaeological Sample Metadata Profile (Ver. 1.0) and who are considered the authors of this work are:

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We also acknowledge the following former CoP members for their contributions to this work: Stéphanie Duchêne, Barbara Trichereau, and Andrew Williams.

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1. Project

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The title (and any alternatives) of the site or project.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

188 Cumberland Street, The Rocks.

Sub-properties:

- [1.1 projectDescription](#)
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1.1 projectDescription

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

A brief summary of the main aims and objectives of the research project (or alternative process) from which the sample collection arose together with a brief summary description of the sample content.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Small historical archaeological project in The Rocks, Sydney, uncovering relics of domestic and commercial life from the 1820s through to the late 20th century.

1.2 siteLocation

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The location from where the sample was collected, as accurately as possible—noting that this can be sensitive information and in such cases, generalized information should be provided to the level it is safe to publish (e.g. spatial region). Ideally, GPS or lat-long coordinates should be included using WGS-84 format in decimal degrees.

If the country, region, county, town or village covered by the sample collection is specified, then this should include current and contemporary name(s) and, where possible, a standardized reference such as the [Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names](#) or [GeoNames](#) should be used.

If names or administrative units change during the time period of the sample collection, they should be recorded separately. Site coordinates can also be entered as a National Grid Reference in a number of different ways (e.g., as a point, line, polygon).

It is helpful to include the full postal code of the site, if applicable.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

At least one of the below geolocation subproperties must be included.

Additional information concerning the site location should be captured in the free-text locationPlace subproperty.

1.2.1 locationPoint

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.1.1 pointLongitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.1.2 pointLatitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.2 locationBox

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.2.1 westBoundLongitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.2.2 eastBoundLongitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.2.3 southBoundLatitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.2.4 northBoundLatitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.3 locationPlace

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.4 locationPolygon

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.4.1 polygonPoint

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.4.1.1 pointLongitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.4.1.2 pointLatitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.4.2 inPolygonPoint

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.4.2.1 pointLongitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.2.4.2.2 pointLatitude

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

These subproperties follow from the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) for the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the definitions of these subproperties.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for examples of these subproperties.

1.3 agencyIdentifier

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Agency or project site identifier used as a local identifier of the site.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Smithsonian Trinomial, AZ State Museum (ASM) number,...

1.4 siteTemporalCoverage

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The dates/period covered by samples collected at the site, regardless of whether all samples have been (or will be) preserved or registered with persistent identifiers. Use an existing thesaurus where possible, such as the [RCHME Period List](#) or [PeriodO](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Bronze Age, Medieval,...

1.4.1 temporalClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory if siteTemporalCoverage is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for siteTemporalCoverage
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in siteTemporalCoverage
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in siteTemporalCoverage

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

<http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p072r4qmq9s>

Historic England Periods, https://heritagedata.org/live/schemes/eh_period.html

1.5 siteOwner

Obligation: Optional

Definition:

The organization that owns the land on which the sample was collected; the default is 'Private'.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Sydney Harbour Foreshore Authority, Private,...

1.6 siteType

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Type of past activity area(s) identified at the site. An existing controlled vocabulary should be used where possible, such as the [Getty Research Institute Art & Architecture Thesaurus](#) or the [tDAR Data Dictionary](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Cemetery, Cave settlement, Castle, Monastery,...

1.6.1 siteClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory if siteType is used. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for siteType
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in siteType
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in siteType

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

300006891, <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300006891>

tDAR Data Dictionary Site Types,

<https://tdar-arch.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/TDAR/pages/557203/Site+Types>

1.7 Keywords

Obligation: Optional

Definition:

User created values to describe aspects of the site not covered by other metadata.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Coastal, Eroded, Waterlogged,...

2. investigationType

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Lists all investigation types relevant to the resource. Should follow a standard vocabulary such as that provided by the [Intrusive Event](#) concept provided in the [FISH Event Types Thesaurus](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Survey, Excavation,...

Sub-properties:

- [2.1 investigationClassification](#)

2.1 investigationClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory if investigationType is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for investigationType
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in investigationType
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in investigationType

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes/agl_et/concepts/145151

3. investigationDates

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Full date range using RKMS-ISO8601 format, indicating when the archaeological project was carried out or the processing dates, as appropriate. For ongoing or multi-annual investigations specify the dates of the specific project for which the investigation took place.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

2024-01-01/2024-01-31

Sub-properties:

- [3.1 startDate](#)
- [3.2 endDate](#)

3.1 startDate

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Starting date of the investigation using W3CDTF format, as specified in investigationDates.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

2024-01-01

3.2 endDate

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

End date of the investigation using W3CDTF format, as specified in investigationDates.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

2024-01-31

4. collectorExcavator

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Details of the creator(s), compiler(s), funding agencies, or other bodies or people intellectually responsible for the sample collection. Used to properly credit individuals and institutions for their contribution to the resource.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

See subproperties for examples. The Name subproperty is mandatory for each collectorExcavator that is listed.

Sub-properties:

- [4.1 Name](#)
 - [4.1.1 nameType](#)
- [4.2 Forename](#)
- [4.3 Surname](#)
- [4.4 ORCID](#)
- [4.5 Affiliation](#)
- [4.6 ROR](#)

4.1 Name

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The full name of the collectorExcavator. The format for a person's name is: Surname, Forename.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Doe, Jane

Department of History and Archaeology, Macquarie University

4.1.1 nameType

Obligation: Optional

Definition:

The type of Name. Limited to a binary choice of whether Name belongs to a person or an institution.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Personal / Organizational

4.2 Forename

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The first or given name of the creatorExcavator. Used if creatorExcavator is a person.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Jane

4.3 Surname

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The last or family name of the creatorExcavator. Used if creatorExcavator is a person.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Doe

4.4 ORCID

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

If it exists, the ORCID iD that uniquely identifies the creatorExcavator. Used if creatorExcavator is a person.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1584-4316>

4.5 Affiliation

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The organizational or institutional affiliation of the creatorExcavator. Used if creatorExcavator is a person or an institution (e.g., a research department). For the latter, this would likely be the name of its larger/umbrella organization.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Macquarie University

4.6 ROR

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

If it exists, the ROR ID that uniquely identifies the organizational affiliation of the creatorExcavator.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

<https://ror.org/01sf06y89>

5. Publisher

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The organization that is registering the metadata record for the sample.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Archaeology Data Service

Sub-properties:

- [5.1 ROR](#)
-

5.1 ROR

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

If it exists, the ROR ID that uniquely identifies the publishing organization.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

<https://ror.org/04w1khd64>

6. Contributor

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Other individual(s) or organization(s) who have contributed to the collecting, analysis, or managing of the sample.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

See subproperties for examples. The Role and Name subproperties are mandatory for each Contributor that is listed.

Sub-properties:

- [6.1 Role](#)
- [6.2 Name](#)
 - [6.2.1 nameType](#)
- [6.3 Forename](#)
- [6.4 Surname](#)
- [6.5 ORCID](#)
- [6.6 Affiliation](#)
- [6.7 ROR](#)

6.1 Role

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The role that the Contributor played in the sample collection, analysis, or management process. Mandatory if a Contributor is listed.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Allowed values follow the controlled list for the contributorType subproperty in the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the list and examples.

6.2 Name

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The full name of the Contributor. The format for a person's name is: Surname, Forename.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Bloggs, Joe

Research Data Management Division, German Archaeological Institute

6.2.1 nameType

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The type of Name. Limited to a binary choice of whether Name belongs to a person or an institution.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Personal / Organizational

6.3 Forename

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The first or given name of the Contributor. Used if Contributor is a person.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Joe

6.4 Surname

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The last or family name of the Contributor. Used if Contributor is a person.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Bloggs

6.5 ORCID

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

If it exists, the ORCID iD that uniquely identifies the Contributor. Used if Contributor is a person.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2881-2599>

6.6 Affiliation

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The organizational or institutional affiliation of the Contributor. Used if Contributor is a person or an institution (e.g., a research department). For the latter, this would likely be the name of its larger/umbrella organization.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

German Archaeological Institute

6.7 ROR

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

If it exists, the ROR ID that uniquely identifies the organizational affiliation of the Contributor.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

<https://ror.org/041qv0h25>

7. sampleTitle

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Title or name that enables discovery and distinction of the sample. Information may include the basic form of the object, the material(s) that compose to the sample, and any local sample identifiers.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

CRRW FP-6076523-QUS – Bird Fibula Brooch (Bronze), Roman Period

8. Description

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Detailed description of the sample. Should include information about the sample and its collection not captured in other properties. For example, the primary reason for sample collection in terms of analytics.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

1 bag of soil: dark greyish brown with slate, glass, brick, plaster inclusions

9. Subject

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Keywords for the subject content of the sample. Keywords should be taken from standard vocabulary, such as the [English Heritage NMR Monument Types Thesaurus](#), [MDA Archaeological Object Thesaurus](#), or the [Getty Research Institute Art & Architecture Thesaurus](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Palynology, Date Stone,...

Sub-properties:

- [9.1 subjectClassification](#)

9.1 subjectClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory if Subject is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for Subject
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in Subject
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in Subject

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

300251145, <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300251145>

FISH Thesaurus of Monument Types,
https://heritagedata.org/live/schemes/eh_tmt2.html

10. otherIdentifier

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The project / reference / catalogue / sample number(s) used to identify the sample on site.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

188CUMB-187

11. collectionDate

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Date when sample was collected following W3CDTF format. Multiple samples from the same source should be registered separately and then connected through the Relations property metadata. May optionally include the time at which the sample was collected.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

2024-01-15T08:34:49Z

12. collectionMethod

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

How the sample was collected. Where possible, terminology should follow a standard vocabulary.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Core, Scoop,...

Sub-properties:

- [12.1 collectionMethodClassification](#)
- [12.2 sampleHousing](#)
- [12.3 samplePhoto](#)
 - [12.3.1 photoLicence](#)

12.1 collectionMethodClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory if collectionMethod is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for collectionMethod
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in collectionMethod
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in collectionMethod

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

None

12.2 sampleHousing

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

What the sample was collected in. If the housing changes at the other stages of the lifecycle, then sampleHousing may be updated to include the new housing and the lifecycle stage (e.g., during analysis or storage). Mandatory if collectionMethod is included.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Ziplock bag, Sterile container,...

Polycarbonate storage box (long-term archival)

12.3 samplePhoto

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

A link to a photograph of the sample or its bag/container at the time of collection. Recommendations for photographing archaeological artefacts are given in [this guidance document](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/5/53/Early_Medieval_Button_Brooch_%28FindID_137891%29.jpg

12.3.1 photoLicence

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Any licence information concerning reuse of the sample photograph. Mandatory if samplePhoto is included.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

CC BY-SA 4.0

13. stratigraphicContext

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The site or project specific identifier of the stratigraphic or survey unit from which the sample was collected. This property is considered mandatory in the case of samples collected during surveys and excavations.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

A301

Sub-properties:

- [13.1 contextType](#)
 - [13.1.1 contextClassification](#)
- [13.2 siteDiagram](#)
 - [13.2.1 siteDiagramLicence](#)
- [13.3 Zone](#)
- [13.4 soilTexture](#)
 - [13.4.1 soilClassification](#)
- [13.5 contextDescription](#)

13.1 contextType

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The type of stratigraphicContext. Should follow a vocabulary reference such as the [Getty Research Institute Art & Architecture Thesaurus](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Grave, Storage pit, Sunken house,...

13.1.1 contextClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory if contextType is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for contextType
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in contextType
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in contextType

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

300005907, <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300005907>

13.2 siteDiagram

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Image of site that makes the exact location of the sample clear.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332757371/figure/fig1/AS:11431281416999457@1746102125477/Map-of-the-archaeological-site-of-S-Omobono-showing-sample-collection-locations-and-the.tif>

13.2.1 siteDiagramLicence

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Any licence information concerning reuse of the site diagram. Mandatory if siteDiagram is included.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

CC BY 4.0

13.3 Zone

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Identifier(s) of the zone(s) from which the sample was collected. Such that relevant, investigation-specific information may be captured, 'zone' is deliberately left undefined. It may be an area/quadrant, trench, or otherwise. Moreover, identifiers from zones at different granularities may be included. In this latter case, it is recommended to include the type of zone alongside each identifier.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Area: D24, Trench: VII, Transect: S9/E

13.4 soilTexture

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Texture as per agreed standards, such as the [FAO World Reference Base for Soil Resources](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Sandy silt

13.4.1 soilClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory if soilTexture is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for soilTexture
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in soilTexture
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in soilTexture

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

300014341, <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300014341>

13.5 contextDescription

Obligation: Optional

Definition:

Additional information about the stratigraphicContext.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

A301 was the third layer in Cesspit 12.

14. sampleDepth

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Depth of the sample within the stratigraphicContext.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

10

Sub-properties:

- [14.1 depthUnits](#)
 - [14.2 depthReferencePoint](#)
-

14.1 depthUnits

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Units used to measure depth of sample. Mandatory if sample depth is included.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

mm, cm, m,...

14.2 depthReferencePoint

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The reference point in the context from where the sample depth was measured.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Top lens

15. sampleWeight

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Weight at the point of collection, before analysis.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

653

Sub-properties:

- [15.1 weightUnits](#)
- [15.2 weightConditions](#)

15.1 weightUnits

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Units used to measure sample weight. Mandatory if sample weight is included.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

kg, g, mg,...

15.2 weightConditions

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Additional information about the state of the sample at the time the weight was measured.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Cleaned, With soil, Dried, Humid,...

16. sampleMaterialType

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The type(s) of material(s) that compose the sample. Should follow a controlled vocabulary such as the [Getty Research Institute Art & Architecture Thesaurus](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Ceramic, Fauna, Metal, Soil, Bone,...

Sub-properties:

- [16.1 materialClassification](#)

16.1 materialClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The vocabulary used for classification of the material type. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for sampleMaterialType
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in sampleMaterialType
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in sampleMaterialType

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

300011798, <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300011798>

17. Colour

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Colour(s) of the sample following a standard vocabulary such as the Munsell colour system.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

2.5YR 3/3 Dark Reddish Brown

Sub-properties:

- [17.1 colourClassification](#)
- [17.2 colouredArea](#)

17.1 colourClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The vocabulary used for classification of the sample colour(s). Mandatory if Colour is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for Colour
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in Colour
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in Colour

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Munsell, 'By eye',...

17.2 colouredArea

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The area of the sample for which colours are being described.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Urn handle

18. absoluteDating

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Numerical age or range of the sample. Dates and ranges should follow W3CDTF and RKMS-ISO8601, respectively.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

-300/-150

Sub-properties:

- [18.1 datingMethod](#)
 - [18.2 datingClassification](#)
-

18.1 datingMethod

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Should follow a standard vocabulary such as that provided by the [Dating Techniques](#) concept provided in the [FISH Archaeological Sciences Thesaurus](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Radiocarbon dating

18.2 datingClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The vocabulary used for the absolute dating method. Mandatory if datingMethod is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for datingMethod
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in datingMethod
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in datingMethod

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

300054717, <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300054717>

FISH Archaeological Sciences Thesaurus,
<https://heritagedata.org/live/schemes/560.html>

19. relativeDating

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Cultural and user created values for relative dating of the sample. Should follow a standard vocabulary such as the [Getty Research Institute Art & Architecture Thesaurus](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

PaleoIndian, Archaic,...

Sub-properties:

- [19.1 datingClassification](#)

19.1 datingClassification

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The vocabulary used for the relative dating method. Mandatory if relativeDating is included. Should contain at least one, and ideally all, of the following:

- a. The name of the standard vocabulary being used for relativeDating
- b. The URI of the standard vocabulary being used
- c. The URI of the exact term used in relativeDating
- d. The classification code (if one exists) of the exact term used in relativeDating

Note that a&b and c&d are normally pair values, so it is encouraged to include both where possible. For machine readability, and if you are using a FAIR vocabulary, it is recommended to include the URI values, with c, being optimal.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

300016965, <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300016965>

20. generalKeywords

Obligation: Optional

Definition:

User created values to describe aspects of the sample not covered by other metadata.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Polished, Fragmentary, Hand-built,...

21. currentStatus

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Information concerning the current status of the sample. Does the sample still exist? Was it discarded/destroyed in analysis or otherwise? Has it degraded over time or been lost?

Note that it is recommended to also indicate the date that the value of the status was revised.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Archived, Destroyed,...

Sub-properties:

- [21.1 storageLocation](#)
- [21.2 accessConditions](#)
 - [21.2.1 accessType](#)

21.1 storageLocation

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Current physical storage location of sample.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Archaeological collection of The British Museum.

21.2 accessConditions

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

What the access rights are to the sample and/or who to contact about access.
Access rights should ideally follow a controlled vocabulary.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Open access, Embargoed,...

Access to the sample is upon request. Please contact the Department of History and Archaeology, Macquarie University.

21.2.1 `accessType`

Obligation: Optional

Definition:

Whether the sample is publicly available or only for private use. A binary choice to enable a quick understanding of access rights.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Public / Private

22. Relations

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

Relationships to other research outputs/entities that are identified by a globally unique identifier. In particular, if the sample was derived or subsampled from a parent source, and any references to analytical results (datasets).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

See subproperties for examples and obligations.

Sub-properties:

- [22.1 relatedIdentifier](#)
- [22.2 identifierType](#)
- [22.3 relationType](#)
- [22.4 relatedMetadataScheme](#)
- [22.5 relatedResource](#)

22.1 relatedIdentifier

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The globally unique identifier assigned to the related research output/entity. Mandatory if Relations is used.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

10.61585/m-tx-202500660

22.2 identifierType

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The type of globally unique identifier that is assigned to the related research output/entity. Mandatory if Relations is used.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Allowed values follow the controlled list for the relatedIdentifierType subproperty in the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the list and examples.

22.3 relationType

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

The relationship between the current sample being described and the related research output/entity. Mandatory if Relations is used.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Allowed values follow the controlled list for the relationType subproperty in the DataCite Metadata Schema. Please see the [documentation](#) of the latest version of the DataCite Schema for the list and examples.

22.4 relatedMetadataScheme

Obligation: Mandatory

Definition:

Mandatory only if either the HasMetadata or IsMetadataFor relationType is used, should not be used in other cases.

If the sample has already been described using a metadata schema specific to your institution, discipline, or community, this may be linked using the 'HasMetadata' relationType attribute. Typically, this will take the form of a web-hosted metadata file (via an API endpoint), in which case the 'URL' identifierType should be used. The name, URI, and type of the related schema should be included.

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Darwin Core Archive, <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/guides/text/index.htm>, DwC-A

22.5 relatedResource

Obligation: Recommended

Definition:

The type of the related research output/entity. Should follow a controlled vocabulary; for example, that used for the resourceTypeGeneral property in the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#).

Allowed values, examples, other constraints:

Dataset, JournalArticle, PhysicalObject,...